

Lipoma of the Ovary: A Histopathological Analysis- A Case Report

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Abstract:

Lipomas are benign tumors predominantly composed of mature adipose tissue. While commonly found in subcutaneous locations, their occurrence within the ovary is exceedingly rare. We present a detailed histopathological examination of a lipoma of the ovary in a 45-year-old female patient. The specimen was subjected to gross and microscopic analysis, revealing the characteristic features of mature adipocytes and confirming the diagnosis of ovarian lipoma. This case report provides insights into the histological presentation of ovarian lipomas and emphasizes the importance of accurate diagnosis through histopathological examination.

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Introduction

Ovarian lipomas are uncommon neoplasms that pose diagnostic challenges due to their infrequent occurrence. A precise histopathological assessment is essential for confirming the diagnosis and distinguishing ovarian lipomas from other ovarian tumors. [1] This case report of an ovarian lipoma that was found incidentally during abdominal hysterectomy for uterine fibroids in a 45-year-old woman aims to present the histopathological characteristics of an ovarian lipoma and contribute to the existing literature on this rare entity.

Case Presentation:

A 45-year-old woman G4P4L4A0 with last delivery 17 years back was admitted to the department of obstetrics and gynecology Sardar Patel medical college, Bikaner with a history of excessive menstrual bleeding & pain abdomen during menstrual cycle since last 8 months. She had a history of bilateral tubal ligation 17 yrs back.

Gynecological examination was normal. Past medical history was unremarkable. Ultrasound was done which showed fibroids in LUS. She was managed with Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy. [2]

Specimen of total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy measured 11x7x5cms. On cutting endometrial canal was identified with maximum endo-myometrial thickness of 2cm. A small intramural fibroid measuring 2cm in diameter was identified with cut surface grey white and whorled. Left ovary measured 3x2x1cms with cut surface grey white and solid. A well-circumscribed, grayish-white polypoidal mass was identified on the outer surface of left ovary, measuring 0.5cm in diameter. Cut surface of polypoidal mass was yellowish-white and exhibited no areas of necrosis or hemorrhage. Right sided ovary measured 2.5x2.5x1cm having partly cystic and partly grey white cut surface.

Figure – 1 Gross picture of lipoma on the surface of the Left ovary

Microscopy: Microscopic analysis of the tissue sections revealed a well-defined encapsulated mass composed predominantly of mature adipocytes. The adipocytes exhibited uniform round-to-

polygonal shapes with small, centrally located nuclei and abundant clear cytoplasm. No evidence of cellular atypia, mitotic activity, or necrosis was observed. The adipocytes were interspersed with delicate fibrous septa.

Figure 2A: Photomicrograph of H&E stained section of the lipoma of the left ovary (4X)

Figure 2B: Photomicrograph of H&E stained section of the lipoma of the left ovary. (10X)

Discussion

The adipose tissue is not native to the ovary. Embryonic misplacement of fat cells and ovarian stromal cell metaplasia into fat cells are two of the important proposed mechanisms. [3] The majority of ovarian lipomas are a component of adult teratomas, and their treatment may differ from that of a simple ovarian lipoma. Teratoma is the tumor that has tissue from all three germinal layers and which also contain adipose tissues and other parts such bone, cartilage, the skin adnexae and others. However, even with the extensive sampling, tissues from additional germ layers were not found in our patient. Hence, the diagnosis of a lipoma was considered over teratoma.

Adipose tissues can be a component of malignant mixed Mullerian tumors (carcinosarcoma), but these are malignant. Malignancy is ruled out by the lack of nuclear atypia, lipoblast, and atypical mitoses in the microscopic examination. In our situation, the tumor lacked any microscopic signs of malignancy.

The histopathological features observed in this case are consistent with a diagnosis of ovarian lipoma. The microscopic appearance of ovarian lipoma is similar to the other lipomatous tumor arising in other parts of the body. Ovarian lipomas must be differentiated from other ovarian tumors, such as teratomas and liposarcomas through careful histopathological examination as management and prognosis of benign and malignant adipocytic tumors can be different. Pure ovarian lipomas,

although rare are readily recognized and do not present a diagnostic problem. They can be differentiated from stromal fat-cell hyperplasia by the presence of well-demarcated capsules at their periphery. [4]

Conclusion

Histopathological evaluation remains the cornerstone for accurate diagnosis of ovarian lipomas. Recognition of the characteristic features of mature adipocytes and appropriate immunohistochemical staining aid in distinguishing lipomas from other ovarian neoplasms. Despite their rarity, ovarian lipomas should be considered in the differential diagnosis of ovarian masses, and histopathological analysis plays a pivotal role in providing definitive diagnosis and guiding clinical management.

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